

"TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL POSITION AMONG FUTURE TEACHERS"

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Annotation. The existing professional training programs for a future teacher are not fully focused on the subjective personal experience of students, are not addressed to their initial ideas about pedagogical activity, and do not take into account the students' own experience. Subjective experience in the learning process is constantly transformed, modified according to the accumulative principle.

Keywords. Hollow, peace, preparation, knowledge

Each training cycle adds new knowledge, techniques and ways of working, the next step is based on the formulation and solution of educational and professional tasks by students, while updating existing knowledge and mastering new elements of professional experience. Pedagogical practice for students is a serious exam, showing the level of their theoretical training and at the same time a school of practical skills, in which they make their first attempts at self-realization, master the operational structures and experience of professional pedagogical activity, subject to the consistent formation and development of professional skills. Pedagogical practice, as a special type of activity, requires students to actualize their individual experience gained in theoretical and practical classes, to integrate knowledge and professional skills that most contribute to the development of an acmeological position.

Personal qualities and professional skills, motivation for professional achievements are the main components in the professional activity of the future teacher. This key idea is the basis of the concept of the program developed by us for the workshop "Acmeological Position of the Future Teacher". It is necessary to use these skills for practical purposes with high efficiency, to master new algorithms and methods for solving professional problems. The methodological basis for constructing the content of the seminar was the scientific provisions on the meaning-forming role of professional knowledge and skills in self-development, on the decisive role of internal determination in the process of self-improvement, on the ascending nature of human development as a subject of activity. The formed acmeological position is a determinant of improving the quality of professional training of future teachers. The pedagogical tasks used in the seminar, trainings, role-playing games, as well as tasks in which the student realizes his attitude to the future profession, transforming his inner world,

require the formation of a certain system of knowledge, skills and abilities in students to solve professional problems that are adequate to educational goals and age characteristics of schoolchildren, knowledge about the ways of personal self-development, about the mechanisms that contribute to the movement towards success, which should serve as a kind of start for self-organization and self-development of the individual. На семинарских и практических занятиях в процессе педагогической практики экспериментальной группой были практически закреплены изученные знания, необходимые в профессионально-педагогической деятельности будущего учителя, сформированы профессиональные умения и профессионально-личностные качества, необходимые для осуществления профессионально-педагогической деятельности.

Определена связь между основными группами задач, ориентированными на становление базовой (общепрофессиональной) компетентности будущего учителя и акмеологической позицией. Взаимосвязь показывает, что студент, умеющий конструировать педагогические задачи ориентирован на успех в профессиональной деятельности, на дальнейшее развитие своего творческого потенциала. Наиболее высоким показателям сформированное™ умений решать профессиональные задачи соответствует достаточно высокий уровень развития акмеологической позиции.

Экспериментальным путем подтверждена эффективность модели педагогической практики, способствующая развитию акмеологической позиции будущего учителя и определяющая установку на саморазвитие, на реализацию профессионального потенциала будущего учителя.

Заключение

Тенденция современного образования к возрастанию субъектно-творческого начала в профессионально-педагогической деятельности требует высокого уровня развития акмеологической позиции педагога. В результате проведенного исследования достигнута основная цель — теоретически обоснованы и экспериментальным путем проверены педагогические условия, способствующие развитию акмеологической позиции будущего учителя в процессе педагогической практики.

Проведенное исследование позволило сделать следующие выводы:

Акмеологическая позиция будущего учителя — это интегративная характеристика личности, ориентированная на высокие результаты и достижения педагогического труда, на развитие творчества учителя и

ученика при наличии устойчивых г. At seminars and practical classes in the process of pedagogical practice, the experimental group practically consolidated the studied knowledge necessary in the professional and pedagogical activities of the future teacher, formed the professional skills and professional and personal qualities necessary for the implementation of professional and pedagogical activities.

The relationship between the main groups of tasks focused on the formation of the basic (general professional) competence of the future teacher and the acmeological position is determined. The relationship shows that a student who is able to design pedagogical tasks is focused on success in professional activities, on the further development of his creative potential. The highest indicators of the formed [™] skills to solve professional problems correspond to a fairly high level of development of the acmeological position.

The effectiveness of the model of pedagogical practice, which contributes to the development of the acmeological position of the future teacher and determines the orientation towards self-development, towards the realization of the professional potential of the future teacher, has been experimentally confirmed.

Conclusion

The trend of modern education towards an increase in the subject-creative beginning in professional and pedagogical activity requires a high level of development of the acmeological position of the teacher. As a result of the study, the main goal was achieved - theoretically substantiated and experimentally tested pedagogical conditions that contribute to the development of the acmeological position of the future teacher in the process of pedagogical practice.

The study made it possible to draw the following conclusions:

The acmeological position of the future teacher is an integrative characteristic of the personality, focused on high results and achievements of pedagogical work, on the development of the creativity of the teacher and student in the presence of stable humanistic motives for professional activity.

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